

eCraft2Learn

Digital Fabrication and Maker Movement in Education
Making Computer – supported Artefacts from Scratch

Deliverable D4.4

The unified user interface - A software solution for 3D design, programming and making computer-supported artefacts (M18)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 731345.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Acronym: **eCraft2Learn**
Title: Digital Fabrication and Maker Movement in Education: Making Computer-supported Artefacts from Scratch
Coordinator: University of Eastern Finland
Reference: 731345
Type: RIA
Program: HORIZON 2020
Theme: Technologies for Learning and Skills
Start: 01. January, 2017
Duration: 24 months
Website: <http://www.project.ecraft2learn.eu/>
E-Mail: office@ecraft2learn.eu

Consortium: **University of Eastern Finland**, Finland, (UEF), Coordinator
Edumotiva, Greece (EDUMOTIVA)
Mälardalen University of Sweden, Sweden (MDH)
Zentrum für Soziale Innovation, Austria, (ZSI)
The University of Oxford, United Kingdom, (UOXF)
SYNYO GmbH, Austria, (SYNYO)
University of Padua, Italy, (UNIPD)
Technopolis City of Athens, Greece (TECHNOPOLIS)
Evothings, Sweden (EVOTHINGS)
Arduino, Sweden (ARD)
Ultimaker, United Kingdom (ULTIMAKER)
Linnaeus University, Sweden, (LNU)

DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

Number:	D4.4
Title:	The unified user interface - A software solution for 3D design, programming and making computer-supported artefacts
Lead beneficiary:	UOXF
Work package:	WP4
Dissemination level:	Public (PU)
Type	Other (O)
Due date:	30.06.2018
Submission date:	30.06.2018
Authors:	Ken Kahn [UOXF], Baran Cürüklü [MDH]
Contributors:	All consortium partners
Reviewers:	Afshin Ameri [MDH]

Version Control

Version	Date	Person in charge (Organization)	Changes	Quality Assurance
1	15.06.2018	Ken Kahn (UOXF)	Redefining the document structure and content	Afshin Ameri [MDH]
2	28.06.2018	Ken Kahn (UOXF)	Final version	Baran Cürüklü [MDH]

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action under Grant Agreement No 731345.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors, and does not in any way represent the view of the European Commission or its services.

TABLE OF CONTENT

Executive summary.....	7
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Unified User Interface (version 2)	9
2.1. User interface approach and design	9
2.2. Interacting with Unified User Interface	10
2.2.1. Interacting with Tiles.....	10
2.2.2. Launching a Tool in a UUI Window.....	11
2.2.3. User Login to UUI.....	13
2.2.4. Teacher Notes	13
2.3. The Unified User Interface (version 2)	13
2.4. The Unified User Interface (remaining enhancements).....	14
3 Conclusion.....	14

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1 - eCraft2Learn craft and project-based methodology (the 5 stages)	8
Figure 2 - The UUI is a 2D space.....	9
Figure 3 - The two states of a tile..	10
Figure 4 - The help dialog for the Snap! Tool..	11
Figure 5 - TinkerCad running in a window inside eCraft2Learn environment.....	12
Figure 6 - The UUI with the Active Tools Panel visible.	12
Figure 7 - The login page.....	13

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the work that is carried out in order to design and implement the second version (version 2) of the unified user interface (UUI), which plays a central role in the eCraft2Learn project. This interface addresses interaction with 3D technologies (modelling, visualisation, simulation, and printing) as well as DIY electronics (wiring, programming, debugging), thus provides feedback on design and design conditions of the project to the learner. The same interface will also be used by the teachers to monitor and guide the learner. By designing one multi-purpose interface, for all users, the intention is to provide a holistic view of the process to the users as well as facilitate the involvement of the teachers in the learning process.

1 INTRODUCTION

The UUI plays a central role in the eCraft2Learn project. It is the prime tool for letting the learners and the coaches/teachers to access the technological solutions that are offered. This interface is flexible enough to address needs in both formal and informal settings, although the rest of this document primarily describes issues associated with the former.

All of the digital tools that are required in the five stage craft and project-based methodology of eCraft2Learn are accessed by the UUI. These steps include ideation, planning, creation, program and sharing.

eCraft2Learn Learning Methodology

eCraft2Learn is an ecosystem which is based on craft and project based teaching methods. This methodology includes five stages, which together guide the learner from an idea to developing and showcasing, through sharing, the final solution (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - eCraft2Learn craft and project-based methodology (the 5 stages)

- **Ideation:** The learners explore the world to find challenges. This exploration can be in the physical or virtual world (i.e. online communities).
- **Planning:** The learners collect information and material. They also start making project plans.
- **Creation:** Through a co-design and co-creation process, the learners start creating their solutions. This stage might involve many different technologies such as do-it-yourself (DIY) electronics, visualization, simulation and 3D printing.
- **Programming:** Learners add functionality to their crafted artefacts through high-level programming languages.
- **Sharing:** By sharing the solutions on online communities, the learners can learn from other projects, while receiving feedback from designers, engineers and programmers.

Each of the aforementioned stages requires a different set of tools and materials. Developing a central place (software) for managing these stages is the aim of the educational extension in eCraft2Learn. Such a solution will make it easier to manage the learners' co-creation project work and also can provide then additional tools to improve their projects even further.

The UI plays a central role in this context since its aim is to allow the users to go between different tools smoothly. Another important feature of this interface is that it collects information about the activities of the users. This information is used in the learning analytics part. The learning analytics solution will collect data from technical parts of the eCraft2Learn framework, such as 3D printers and programming environment, as well as from learners' and teachers' interactions with the (UI).

2 UNIFIED USER INTERFACE (VERSION 2)

The UI is a portal to a wide range of tools that covers the eCraft2Learn five pedagogic stages. The majority of these tools are integrated in that they appear as elements of the UI that can be treated as sub-windows. The integration also includes data gathering for learning analytics and file sharing. The educational extension which hosts abovementioned tools, and its integration with the UI is described in detailed in D4.3 and a user manual for its use and a video demo are included in D4.5. As can be seen below (Figure 2), the most evident feature is the clusters of set of tools for each of the five stages (Ideation/Imagine, Plan, Create, Program, Share) of the eCraft2Learn craft- and project-based learning methodology. As can be seen all tool are visible and available, at the same time the five stages of the methodology is evident.

Figure 2 - The UI is a 2D space.

2.1. USER INTERFACE APPROACH AND DESIGN

The Unified User Interface can be found at <https://ecraft2learn.github.io/uui/>. We decided to use the Metro style ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Metro_\(design_language\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Metro_(design_language))) familiar from Windows 10 and elsewhere. It is structured around the five pedagogic stages of eCraft2Learn. Each tool provides both tool tips and a more detailed help page. We decided to highlight those tools that are tightly integrated and recommended by making their icons much bigger than other tools. When possible, tools are launched as sub-windows of the interface. These can be minimised, maximised, and closed. When there is no web-based version of a tool the Unified User Interface launches a sub-window describing with images and videos how to launch the desired tool. The UI updates logs of user actions on one of our servers to facilitate learning analytics.

The UI is hosted on github.io to facilitate collaboration and versioning. Github.com is the free open source code repository that is used in the project. The HTML, CSS, and JavaScript files are automatically

copied from github.com to github.io where they are served as web pages. It is highly robust and reliable. Being free means the site will remain after the project and its funding has ended.

The UUI website only serves static files and hence requires no maintenance on our part. Updates and security is handled by Github. In order to collect data for learning analytics JavaScript code was added to make AJAX calls to a project server in Finland that stores the user logs in a database.

By relying only upon static web pages the UUI can easily be run using the local file system or local web server in situations where there isn't reliable Internet access. The project also provides local copies of those web-based tools that are open source. The plan is to store user log data locally to be uploaded subsequently to our server when there is no Internet access.

To implement the popular Metro style interface, the project group decided to build upon Metro UI CSS (<https://metroui.org.ua/>). It was developed with the advice of Microsoft (the original designers of this UI style) and includes general styles, grid, layouts, typography, over twenty components, and over three hundred built-in icons. Metro UI CSS uses the MIT open source licensing model.

2.2. INTERACTING WITH UNIFIED USER INTERFACE

2.2.1. INTERACTING WITH TILES

There are 3 different ways to interact with a tile: hovering the mouse over a tile, clicking a tile and clicking the question mark on top of the tile. Hovering a mouse over a tile shows a short description of that tile on it. This can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - The two states of a tile. The right one shows the tile while a mouse is hovering on it. This activates a short description text about that tool.

Clicking the question mark on top-right corner of a tile, opens a small dialog which explains that tool in more detail. The text might contain links that you can follow to learn more about a tool. As an example, Figure 4 shows the help dialog for the Snap! Tool on the UUI.

Figure 4 - The help dialog for the Snap! Tool. The help dialogs can be accessed by clicking on the question mark located on the top-right corner of each tile.

Clicking a tile will do one of the following:

- Opens the tool in a new window inside eCraft2Learn UII.
- Opens the tool in a new browser window/tab.
- Shows a short video and description on how to launch the tool from the main operating system.

2.2.2. LAUNCHING A TOOL IN A UII WINDOW

At the moment only some tools are launched in this way. They are: Coggle, TinkerCad, Snap!, Snap4Arduino and Thingiverse. Launching a tool inside a UII window allows you to access other tools directly from the UII without the need to move between different operating system windows or browser tabs. Figure 5 shows TinkerCad launched in a UII window.

It is possible to close, maximize and minimize the window, using the three command buttons on the top right corner of the window.

Maximizing a window: Click on the middle button on the top-right corner of the window. By using this option, you allow the tool window to use all the screen space possible. Clicking on this button again bring the window back to its original size.

Closing a window: Click on the X mark on the top right corner of the window. Remember that closing a window ends the session with that tool and the next time that you open that tool you may need to reload/reopen your project. If you want to keep your workspace open in the tool and temporarily use another tool, then use the minimize option.

Figure 5 - TinkerCad running in a window inside eCraft2Learn environment

Minimizing a window: Click on the third button from right on the top-right corner of the window. This hides the window from your view, giving you access to full interface of the UI. The contents of the window and your project stay active and a small icon representing that tool is added to the active tools panel at the bottom of the page.

Figure 6 - The UII with the Active Tools Panel visible.

The active tools panel (Figure 6) contains a list of all the minimized tools for easy access by the user. Please note that it is possible to launch a tool several times (for example if the user wants to open two different files in the same tool).

2.2.3. USER LOGIN TO UUI

The login page is automatically shown on the first access to the interface. Simply input your username and choose your pilot site from the list. Make sure to always use the same username. Figure 7 shown the login page.

Figure 7 - The login page

2.2.4. TEACHER NOTES

In the login page make sure that the students understand the importance of using the same user name for subsequent logins. This helps the data analytics and debugging systems to give a better feedback to the user. In next version of UUI, this will be replaced by a user authentication system.

2.3. THE UNIFIED USER INTERFACE (VERSION 2)

Many changes influenced by participatory design with teachers and students have been made since version 1 (M9):

1. A repository for student project files has been integrated to facilitate sharing and versioning
2. Customisation of the interface and list of resources by teachers
3. Integration of Google Translate provides localised versions
4. Integration of additional tools including a search tool for ideation, a task to-do list tool, an ideation/planning drawing tool, project status, and OER resource browsing and search.
5. We have developed a version that can run on a local web server for users without a reliable Internet connection
6. A feedback tool for user tool feedback
7. A tool to capture student reflection via answers to questions authored by teachers

2.4. THE UNIFIED USER INTERFACE (REMAINING ENHANCEMENTS)

Enhancements in progress include:

1. When feasible tools are launched with the up-to-date state from the current project
2. Further customisation of the interface and list of tools by teachers
3. A searchable repository of shared eCraft2Learn projects
4. Integration with information coming from the learning analytics component
5. Integration of a badge system
6. Integration of the sharing tool

3 CONCLUSION

This document and accompanying videos demonstrated the second version of the unified user interface. This version demonstrates integration with the educational extension, thus the tools to support the five stages of eCraft2Learn methodology. The set of functionalities were selected to provide the basics for the rounds of pilot tests. The results of the pilot studies continues to provide useful insight into further development of the UUI as well as the rest of the system.